

A NOTE ON THE BASICITY AND MOLECULAR WEIGHT OF SHELLAC.

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The basicity and the molecular weight of the two main constituent resin acids of shellac, *viz.*, the pure lac resin and the soft resin of lac, have been ascertained from a study of their behaviour with caustic alkali. An acid potassium salt of the pure lac resin has been isolated by partial neutralisation of the resin with caustic potash and its properties studied.

A knowledge of the basicity and molecular weight of the constituent acids in shellac is an important step towards the study of its constitution. Gardner and his co-workers (*Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1933, 25, 696) have found the molecular weight of bleached shellac to be about 1000, whilst work at this Institute (*Ann. Rep. Indian Lac. Res. Inst.*, 1937-38, p. 3; Bhattacharya and Sen, *Proc. Indian Sci. Cong.* Part III, 1939) indicated that the ether-soluble soft resin and the insoluble pure lac resin have molecular weights of about 500 and 1900 respectively.

When an alcoholic solution of dewaxed shellac is treated with only 70% of KOH required to completely neutralise it, the latter remains clear on dilution with water. This shows that the solution contains no free shellac, which is insoluble in water, but contains a water-soluble acid potassium salt, which could be readily isolated from the solution. This observation is contrary to the view of Weinberger and Gardner (*Ind. Eng. Chem. Anal. Ed.*, 1933, 5, 267) who stated that clear aqueous solutions are obtained only when sufficient alcoholic alkali is added to correspond to the acid number.

On further investigation with both pure and soft resin, it was found that the above observation is only true of pure lac resin but not of soft resin, which is precipitated from the alcoholic solution on addition of water unless completely neutralised. The alkali clarification value of pure lac resin, however, is 60% of the alkali required for complete neutralisation. This suggests that the basicity of pure resin in shellac is more than one. The acid potassium salt of pure lac resin was precipitated by slowly adding a saturated potassium chloride solution to a 20% alcoholic solution of pure lac resin, treated with sufficient aqueous caustic potash (0.5*N*) solution (about 60% of the total acid value)

and then diluted to about eight times with water. As the acid salt dissolves very slowly in cold water, it could be repeatedly washed with cold water until free from chloride and was then dried in a vacuum desiccator. It is a white powder, which turns slightly yellow on complete dehydration and is readily soluble in warm water forming a clear solution. Its acid value was found to be 29.0 which is half the acid value of the desiccated pure lac resin (58.4). The potassium content of the acid salt was found by analysis to be 28.76 (expressed in mg. of caustic potash per g. of the salt). It is concluded, therefore, that pure lac resin is dibasic. Similar conclusions were arrived at for bleached shellac from molecular weight and acid value considerations by Gardner and his co-workers (*loc. cit.*).

The amount of alkali required for the formation of the acid salt of a dibasic acid should be 50% of its acid value, but shellac acids being very weak and insoluble in water, a distinct excess of alkali (about 10% of the total acid value) is required to drive back the hydrolysis of the acid salt and to prevent the precipitation of free shellac on dilution with water. The observed effect of alkali on pure lac resin may be attributed at first sight to some sort of peptising action. But the acid value and the potassium content of the acid salt speak against such a view. Further pure resin dissolves in the aqueous normal potassium salt solution forming the same acid salt. This fact also reveals the dibasic character of the pure resin.

Though undoubtedly there is some colloidal effect present in the behaviour of shellac acids with alkali, as was observed by Wolff (*Farben Z.*, 1922, 27, 3130), that cannot mask the dibasic nature of the pure resin acids, as the foregoing evidences show.

From the known acid value of pure lac resin (58.4), its equivalent weight is 959. Hence, the molecular weight is about 1900, considering it as dibasic. The acid value of pure lac resin generally varies between 55 and 60. Molecular weights, therefore, would be between 1860 and 2000 from the above considerations. From similar considerations soft resin appears to be mono-basic. The acid value of soft resin is generally more than 100 and lies within the limits 100 and 110. Hence, its molecular weight is between 510 and 560, considering it to be mono basic. These values calculated from the consideration of basicity of shellac acids are in good agreement with those previously obtained by the Rast method (*cf. Annual Rep. Indian Lac Res. Inst.*, 1937-38, p. 3), as will be evident from the following table. It should be remembered, however, that as shellac contains both soft and pure resins in the proportion of about 30% and 70%

respectively, its average molecular weight is naturally expected to be lower than that of pure lac resin.

Serial No.	Substance.	Acid value.	Molecular weight from A.V. and basicity.	weight by Rast method.
1.	Pure lac resin (ether extracted).	58.4	1918	1900-2000
2.	Pure lac resin (extracted with ether, dissolved in alcohol, pptd. with water and dried in vacuum)	58.0	1932	1900-2000
3.	Soft resin (ether extracted).	10.3	535	513-556

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